

EAST INDIA COMPANY IN INDIA OFFICE RECORDS IN LONDON

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Abstract:

The historical research, which involves interpreting past events to predict future ones. Historical research design involves synthesizing data from many different sources. The purpose of the research is to further encourage the limited but fruitful cross-disciplinary conversations of recent years. The historical scope of the records begins in 1600, when the East India Company was granted exclusive rights to trade in much of Asia, including the entire Indian subcontinent. The records of the East India Company's Governments in India are probably the best historical materials in the world. The records pertaining from 1600 CE to 1858 CE was safely maintained in the head office at London. The historical scope of the records begins in 1600, when the East India Company was granted exclusive rights to trade in much of Asia, including the entire Indian subcontinent. During its first 100 years, much of the East India Company's energy was involved in maintaining its trade privileges, as it faced competition from domestic and international companies. Although the East India Company was established as a trading company, it became more and more involved in local affairs in India during the early 18th century, and eventually came to hold large swaths of land in the subcontinent. In the year 1682 these records were kept in the East India house in the Leaden Hall Street. In 1720 it was changed to Old Ware-House. In 1771 they appointed keeper for Accounts and Papers. In the year 1833 it was listed out and separated for checking. In 1858 there were 320 tons of records were sold as waste paper. In this Indian Office records we can found the history of England, France, Spain, Holland, Portuguese, Dutch, Turkey, and Burma. After the independence, records from 1600 to 1947 were belonged to Common Wealth of England. Hence, for most 200 years, there was a systematic transfer of wealth from India to Europe. This study bring out the various information's found in the Indian Office Records with special reference to East India Company. In the year 1982, the entire collection was moved to the British Library

Key Words: East India Company, History of the Records, Indian office Record & Classes of Records

Introduction:

The historical research, which involves interpreting past events to predict future ones. Historical research design involves synthesizing data from many different sources. The purpose of the research is to further encourage the limited but fruitful cross-disciplinary conversations of recent years. The arrival of Europeans made a great impact in the history of India. Indian office was a part of the Government of Britain since 1558 CE in India. While the Indian Government had its head office at India, it also had a Government in England which was known as home Government. In this background, in 1599 CE the merchants of London found a merchant guild for carrying out trade with India. If later became the East India merchant guild of English. For more than two centuries they had business contact with India and they ruled. There were so many improvement in the fields of social, economic, political and culture. These and other information are found in the Indian office records. These records are found in the library known as Indian office record library. The records pertaining from 1600 CE to 1858 CE was safely maintained in the head office at London. This study aims at in bringing out the various information found in the Indian office records with special references to East India Company tso bring out the unknown and unexplored area of history in records relating to other Europeans in India from 1475-1824 through this research project.

Meaning of Indian office Record:

The historical scope of the records begins in 1600, when the East India Company was granted exclusive rights to trade in much of Asia, including the entire Indian subcontinent. The records of the East India Company's Governments in India are probably the best historical materials in the world. 1The records pertaining from 1600 CE to 1858 CE was safely maintained in the head office at London. The letter correspondence, treaties and agreements between the East India Company in India and the Home Government of England are called Indian Offices records. Indian office functioned as a department of British Government. An Indian Offices record was nearly 400 years famous historical records. In 1927, Samuel Charles Hill framed the "Catalogue of the Home Miscellaneous Series of India Office records." In this catalogue he includes the documents of East India Company from 1586 to 1918. The India Office Records are a very large collection of documents relating to the administration of India from 1600 to 1947, the period spanning Company and British rule in India. The archive is held in London by the British Library and is publicly accessible.

Historical Background:

The historical scope of the records begins in 1600, when the East India Company was granted exclusive rights to trade in much of Asia, including the entire Indian subcontinent. During its first 100 years, much of the East India Company's energy was involved in maintaining its trade privileges, as it faced

competition from domestic and international companies. Although the East India Company was established as a trading company, it became more and more involved in local affairs in India during the early 18th century, and eventually came to hold large swaths of land in the subcontinent. In the mid-18th century, the Company began to undertake a governmental role in large parts of India, in order to organize the nascent colony to better facilitate trade. In an effort to increase its own involvement in the administration of India, the British Government passed Pitt's India Act in 1784, which established the Board of Control to direct the East India Company in its governing role. In 1858, in the aftermath of the Indian Rebellion of 1857, the British government abolished the East India Company's right to govern India, and brought the subcontinent directly under the control of the British Empire. The India Office, under the direction of the Secretary of State for India, was established to maintain administrative control over the increasingly important colony. In 1937, a separate Burma Office was established to alleviate some of the India Office's administrative burden.

History of the Records:

The India Office Records themselves have a very interesting history. There were different levels of care for the records over the years, but interest in preserving them was established very early. A "Keeper" of East India Company records was appointed in 1771, with a mission to arrange current records and to preserve historical records. Toward the end of the East India Company's governance in India, an increasing number of documents were sent to London and incorporated into the records. In fact, it was one of the most documented administrations ever. However, when the control of India was transferred to the India Office, they set up a committee to review the records provided by the East India Company. On the committee's recommendation, more than 300 tons of records were sold as wastepaper. Although this was certainly a great loss to the collection, there is evidence that many of these records were duplications, or contained very little relevant information. The first attempt to arrange and describe the records occurred in 1879, when George Birdwood published his *Report on the old records of the India Office*. In 1947, the year of Indian independence, ownership of the records transferred to the Foreign and Commonwealth Office of the British government. In 1967, the Office decided to move the records to a new facility on Blackfriars Road, where they were merged with the India Office Library. It was during this transition that the records were transformed into a modern archival collection. A classification system for the records was determined, most of which is still being used. In 1982, the entire collection was moved to the British Library. They are currently a part of the British Library Asia, Pacific and Africa Collections, and they are administered as Public Records, which means that they are available for public consultation in the British Library Reading Rooms.

East India Company:

Indian office functioned as a department of British Government. The East India Company by having trade connection in India, from 1858 CE, found many bodies. They are Advisory body of India, office of the high commissioner of India and Advisory committee. Their activities are recorded in the Company records. The records come from four main sources such as the East India Company (1600-1858), the board of control (1784-1858 CE), the India office (1858-1947 CE) and the Burma office (1937-1948). All the important documents pertaining to the Company from 1600-1858 CE to be studied and analyzed

Types of Records:

The records belong to different categories. They are the original records and copies of the original Records. The information regarding the date on which it was written, the place where they found, by whom they were identified and other relevant materials would be looked into the research. The Miscellaneous Index of Samuel Charles Hill, the guide of Indian office records of Sir William Poster, the sources of the history of the 17th century Britain by Sabad Ahmed Khan and other records which are referred by India office library

Indian office Record in London:

In the year 1682 these records were kept in the East India house in the Leaden Hall Street. In 1720 it was changed to Old Ware-House. In 1771 they appointed keeper for Accounts and Papers. In the year 1833 it was listed out and separated for checking. In 1858 there were 320 tons of records were sold as waste paper. In this Indian Office records we can found the history of England, France, Spain, Holland, Portuguese, Dutch, Turkey, Burma. In 1947 August 15th, after the independence, records from 1600 to 1947 were belonged to Common Wealth of England. In 1920, S.C.Hill started to catalogue the Indian office Record. He followed the work for six years. In 1926 May 6th he was died. After his death his wife followed and finished the work. Birdwood Papers, East Indies Series, Wellesley Papers, James Cumming and Danvers collections, charters, French India and Factory records were found in this catalogues. In Wellesley Papers 23 records were there, in which they found the letter correspondence from Madras and Bombay to Lord Wellesley. Many of the Indian office records have information on the activities of the East India Company. For carrying out so many researches they are considered as the primary sources and such records are going too analyzed.

Structure of India Office:

Many Advisory bodies were found to control the trading activities of the East India Company. Their activities are recorded in the Company records. These records come from four main sources such as the East India Company (1600-1858 CE), the Board of control (1784-1858 CE), the India Office (1858-1947 CE) and

Burma Office (1937-1948 CE). All the important documents pertaining to the Company from 1600-1858 CE would be studied and analyzed.

Divisions in S. C. Hill's Catalogue:

- ✓ 1st to 92 parts contains the East India Company's trading goods.
- ✓ 93 to 190 parts contains East Indies
- ✓ 295 to 315 parts contains Arcot and Carnatic records
- ✓ 457 to 470 parts contains Wellesley manuscripts
- ✓ 526 to 531 parts contains Cunninghams manuscripts
- ✓ 532 to 539 parts contains Press of India
- ✓ 549 to 552 parts contains Parisian wars
- ✓ 577 to 583 parts contains Oudh activities
- ✓ 621 to 624 parts contains Sindhia wars
- ✓ 660 to 680 parts contains Burma wars
- ✓ 724 to 727 parts contains Sir John Kaye's manuscripts
- ✓ 766 to 772 parts contains Thomas Wilkes' various manuscripts.
- ✓ 812 to 813 parts contains Translated records from Pondicherry.
- ✓ 814 parts contains miscellaneous records.

Classes of Records by the India Office in the London Library:

The Indian Office Records are arranged in classes according to the department or agencies which carried out the functions of the India Office and its predecessor institutions.

- ✓ East India Company: charters, deeds, treaties c1550-1950
- ✓ East India Company: minutes of the Court of Directors and Court of Proprietors 1599-1858
- ✓ Council of India minutes and Memoranda 1858-1947
- ✓ East India Company: minutes and Memoranda 1700-1858
- ✓ East India Company: General Correspondence 1602-1859
- ✓ Board of Control records 1784-1858
- ✓ East India Company Factory Records 1784-1858
- ✓ India Office Home Miscellaneous Series 1600-1900
- ✓ records relating to other Europeans in India 1475-1824
- ✓ J & K- East India College and Haileybury records 1749-1925
- ✓ L- India Office Departmental Records 1601-1959
- ✓ M- Burma Office Records 1932-1948
- ✓ N- Returns of Baptisms, marriages and Burials 1698-1969
- ✓ O- Biographical Series 1702-1945
- ✓ P- proceedings and Consultations 1702-1945
- ✓ Q- Commissions, committee and Conference Records 1895-1947
- ✓ R- Records Received in London and incorporated in India Office records 1623-1967
- ✓ S- Linguistic Survey of India 1900-1930
- ✓ V- India Office Records Official Publication Series 1760-1957
- ✓ W, X & Y- India Office Records Map Collections 1700-1960
- ✓ Z- Original Registers and Index Series to the Records 1700-1950.

Conclusion

Hence, for most 200 years, there was a systematic transfer of wealth from India to Europe. This study bringing out the various information found in the Indian Office Records with special reference to East India Company. In the year 1982, the entire collection was moved to the British Library. They are currently part of the British Library Asia, Pacific and Africa collections and they are administered as Public Records, which means that they are available for public consultation in the British Library Reading Rooms.

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